

This is an original manuscript of an article published by Taylor & Francis in
Journal of Environmental Planning and Management on August 1, 2015

available online: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2014.932275>

**A new recoding method for treating protest responses in contingent valuation
studies using travel cost data**

Miguel Ángel Tobarra-González

Department of Economics

Faculty of Business

Polytechnic University of Cartagena

C/ Real 30201 Cartagena (Murcia) España

Teléfono: 34 968 32 56 25 Fax: 34 968 32 57 81 Email: miguel.tobarra@upct.es

Abstract: In this paper, it is proposed one method to recode protest responses applicable to the simple dichotomous format valuation question made to visitors to natural environment in contingent valuation studies. Those respondents that give a protest response but have a travel cost greater than the bid proposed in the valuation question are recoded as an affirmative answer to the proposed payment. The economic justification lies in the minimum willingness to pay for enjoying the environment that travel cost reveals while valuation question tries to obtain information about respondent maximum willingness to pay. Recoding allows to recover information and to improve estimates accuracy. It also avoids computational complexity associated to sample selection models used to avoid biases derived from excluding protest responses.

Keywords: Contingent valuation, protest responses, recoding.

JEL Classification: Q51, D60

1. Introduction

In contingent valuation studies there is a protest response when one respondent affirms that is not willing to make a payment for an environmental good or for an increment in its supply although he/she values it. The motive is not an income or interest lack but the disagreement with any part of contingent market proposed. The reasons can be diverse. Meyerhoff and Liebe (2010) analyse the determinants of protest responses using 254 samples derived from 157 environmental valuation studies and the determinants include the elicitation format, the payment vehicle, the survey method and the geographical origin. Meyerhoff et al. (2013) also study the influence of individual characteristics of the respondent. They conclude that older people, low income groups, people with children and people who cannot be characterized as users of the good have a higher propensity to protest behavior.

A percentage of protest responses appear in all contingent valuation studies and it is accepted as something inherent to them. Szabo (2011) says that one advantage of deliberative monetary valuation over contingent methods is that protest responses are reduced to the half.

A good design of the questionnaire can minimize them. Some authors use explanations to reduce them as much as possible. For example, Bonnicksen and Ladenburg (2009) find that a short ex-ante entreaty reduces the number of protest zero bids without introducing other types of biases in the survey. Atkinson et al. (2012) study the use of scripts as a way to reduce their appearance and they obtain an ambiguous result because although protest responses reduce, there is not a significant effect in the valuation obtained with or without them.

The first problem a researcher faces is to distinguish a real zero from a protest zero bid. The standard procedure is to make follow up questions to differentiate between the two. Some authors show certain instruments to respondents (Jaksonson and Dragun 2001, Strazzera et al. 2003a, Meyerhoff and Liebe 2006) but others as Bateman et al. (2002) are in favour of using open ended questions to distinguish real zeros from protest zero bids. Dziegielewska and Mendelsohn (2007) identified as protesters to those that reject all bids, declare zero on all open-ended valuation questions and hold protest beliefs.

Nonetheless, there is no agreement or protocol about the procedure to use in order to distinguish real zero from protest ones nor about the treatment of protest responses in the subsequent analysis (Meyerhoff and Liebe 2006). The treatment of this kind of answer is an area that is not very developed in the literature.

The problem is that it is not possible to obtain the real value assigned to an environmental good or a change in its supply (Mitchel and Carson, 1989; Bateman et al. 2002). It is not appropriate to consider them as real zeros because they do not correspond to a null valuation but a way to show discontent to the suggested contingent market. The usual approach is to exclude protesters from the valuation analysis (Whittington et al. 1992, Boyle et al. 1993, Jorgensen et al. 1999, Nunes and Van der Bergh 2004, Pemberton et al. 2010, Lindhjem and Navrud 2011 and so on). However, acting in this way can bias the sample representativeness and the valuation result. This have led some authors to advise the use of sample selection models, as the one used for a simple dichotomous choice format in Calia and Strazzera (2001), the one used for a double dichotomous format in Strazzera et al. (2003b) and the one used for a continuous format in the valuation question in Strazzera et al. (2003a), that also propose in this last case the use of the 2-step Heckman estimates in absence of collinearity problems. Other examples of estimates of this kind of models are Brower and Martín-Ortega (2012), in

their study about protest responses induced by polluter pays principle, or Fonta et al. (2010) that carry out a contingent valuation of a malaria control program in Cameroon.

In this paper it is proposed to use the travel cost information to infer a minimum valuation of the studied environmental good (or the change in its supply) and, based on this, recode protest responses. This method results are compared to the results obtained using sample selection models.

The outline of the paper is as follows: the next section briefly describes Calblanque nature reserve, data obtained and values it. Section 3 introduces the proposed method and a new valuation based on it. Section 4 includes sample selection model valuation and compares results to recoding ones. Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. Valuation study of Calblanque nature reserve

Calblanque, Monte de las Cenizas y Peña del Águila nature reserve (Calblanque nature reserve from now on) is located in the southeast of Spain, on the Mediterranean coast. It is protected by the Autonomous Community of Murcia laws (Law of town and country planning and protection of the region of Murcia) due to its biological diversity and the presence of numerous endemic botanic species. At a European Union level, it is a site of Community Importance and it has recently been proposed to be declared as biosphere reserve by UNESCO.

Most of this protected area is mountains although there are also wetlands and strips of beaches. Cliffs and rock walls of limestone mountains constitute other ecosystem inside this protected area. The diversity of habitats and the presence of endemic species lend a

great environmental value to this reserve that has also importance as a touristic and recreational place, especially in summer time due to its attractive beaches from which no building is seen.

A questionnaire designed to collect information that allows the application of travel cost and contingent valuation methods was prepared in order to value this nature reserve.

The valuation was made from a sample of 205 visitors of Calblanque nature reserve, enquired on August 19 and 20 and September 4 and 8, 2012. The sample was divided in four sub-sample of the same size in which the payment proposed varied. These were 5, 10, 15 and 20 euros for an individual yearly entrance. This bid vector was the result of the open-ended responses given by a sample of visitors in an initial survey made before the final enquire process¹. As Clinch and Murphy (2001) point out, a larger number of bids levels would have allowed for greater accuracy in the estimation of the bid curve but each subsample would have been smaller, leading to greater sampling error. A simple dichotomous choice format was chosen (applied by Bishop and Heberlein 1979 for the first time), although next, an open-ended valuation question was included in order to obtain the respondent's maximum willingness to pay. Sampling was random between people that were of age and choosing one person in group.

Among the 205 visitors chosen, 27 expressed protest responses and 7 did not know to answer the valuation question. A response has been considered protest when respondent refused to make a payment three times and justified his refusal with arguments associated to protest responses in contingent valuation literature. Firstly, he was asked if he was willing to pay a yearly entrance if he was sure of money collected was going to be allocated to the nature reserve conservation, without showing an amount. Secondly,

¹ For a detailed process related to bid vector choice, Cooper (1993) and Boyle et al. (1998) can be consulted.

he was asked if he would pay a certain amount of money for a yearly individual entrance if he was sure of money collected was going to be allocated to the nature reserve conservation (simple dichotomous choice format). Finally, he was asked how much he would be willing to pay as a maximum for a yearly individual entrance if he was sure of money collected was going to be allocated to the nature reserve conservation (open ended question). In the three cases it was asked the reason why he was not willing to make a payment in case of refusal. Although first question could be used to ascertain if the respondent was or was not in the market, as in a Spike model (Kriström, 1997), the others two questions were made to give the respondent the possibility to reconsider his answer.

The main reasons stated by respondents, from which it is deduced a protest response, are the refusal to pay for enjoy nature, refusal to pay for a good that belongs to everybody and the distrust politicians really allocate the collection on environment conservation. Table 1 sums up the principal motives that justify the refusal to pay in protest responses and its frequency.

Table 1. Reasons associated to protest responses

It is a good that belongs to everybody	7
It is not willing to pay for enjoy nature	10
Distrust to politicians	5
Others	5
Total	27

Regarding true zero responses, the main reason given was that the amount suggested is too high; only tree people showed they cannot afford to pay anything and two people said they would go to other beaches.

The protest response rate is 13.17% and doesn't know/doesn't answer is 3.4%. They jointly suppose the 16.58% of the sample, rate that is completely normal in this kind of study. 205 face to face interviews are available for the application of travel cost method and only 171 for contingent valuation method due to exclusion of protest and doesn't know/doesn't answer responses. The sample available to make contingent valuation estimates reduces, which could mean using a non-representative sample and o errors obtaining biased estimates.

Table 2 sums up obtained data. It shows descriptive statistics of variables subsequently included in models, for the whole sample, valid responses and protest and doesn't know/doesn't answer responses. These variables are Bid, Ntravel, Cost, Income, Sex, Age, Education and Satisfaction.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of variables used in models, for the whole sample, valid and protest and doesn't know/doesn't answer responses

Variable	Whole sample		Valid responses		Protest and d.k./d.a. responses	
	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
Bid	12.6097	5.5918	12.3391	5.5382	13.9705	5.7444
Ntravel	8.9705	12.7611	8.1403	11.1060	13.2727	18.8419
Cost	9.3493	8.4226	10.1166	8.8304	5.3730	4.0400
Income	1.5030	0.8156	1.5408	0.8284	1.27	0.7022
Sex	0.5219	0.5007	0.5380	0.5000	0.4411	0.5039
Age	40.4146	10.7123	40.3801	10.3282	40.5882	12.6222
Education	2.5170	0.6462	2.5263	0.7460	2.6176	0.6037
Satisfaction	0.3823	0.4871	0.4035	0.4929	0.2727	0.4522

Bid refers to different bids proposed in the simple dichotomous choice valuation question, Ntravel is the number of visits to the nature reserve made by respondent during the last year, Cost is the travel cost that includes fuel and travel time cost for people coming from their residence and also a proportional part of the journey (fuel and time) from their residence to the holiday place for people that are on holidays. Socioeconomic variables include Income (the personal income of respondent in thousands of euros), Sex (codified as 1 for male and 0 for female), Age and Education (codified as 1 for basic studies, 2 for secondary studies and 3 for university studies). Satisfaction would show the respondent satisfaction, codified as 1 for those respondents that indicate that there is nothing in the nature reserve that they would like to change and 0 for those that indicate any matter they don't like and should change in their opinion.

In this section, a discrete choice logit model is estimated in order to obtain the valuation of Calblanque nature reserve and is defined as:

$$\Pr(\text{YESNO}_i=1 \mid \text{Bid}, X) = \Lambda (\alpha\text{Bid}, \delta X) \quad [1]$$

where

$\Lambda (z) = \frac{\exp(z)}{1+\exp(z)}$, is the logistic function, YESNO is a dichotomous variable that can take two values, 1 if it has responded yes to the proposed bid and 0 if it has responded no to the proposed bid and X is a vector of characteristics of the respondent.

The specified Logit model estimated² [1] is:

² Coefficient estimates of the logit model $\Pr(\text{YESNO}_i=1 \mid \text{Bid}_i, X_i) = \Lambda (\delta_0+\alpha\text{Bid}_i+ \delta_1\text{Income}_i+ \delta_2\text{Age}_i+ \delta_3\text{Ntravel}_i+ \delta_4\text{Education}_i+ \delta_5\text{Satisfaction}_i)$ are shown in Table 1of Appendix. It can be tested that Income,

$$\Pr(\text{YESNO}_i=1 \mid \text{Bid}_i, X_i) = \Lambda (\delta_0 + \alpha \text{Bid}_i + \delta_3 \text{Ntravel}_i) \quad [2]$$

Coefficients estimates of the logit model in [2] are shown in Table 3 and are the ones employed in order to calculate the mean value of Maximum Willingness to Pay. It is used the following formula included, for example, in Riera (1994) that follows the pioneering work of Haneman (1984).

$$\text{Mean of Maximum Willingness to Pay} = -(\delta_0 + \delta_3(\text{mean of Ntravel})) / \alpha \quad [3]$$

Table 3. Simple dichotomous format Contingent Valuation Model including significant variables and valid responses

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	Statistic z	P > z	95% Confidence interval	
Bid	-0.1854867	0.0411992	-4.50	0.000	-0.2662356	-0.1047377
Ntravel	0.0965208	0.0359966	2.68	0.000	0.0259687	0.1670728
Constant	3.096639	0.6518228	4.75	0.000	1.81909	4.374188
Dependent Variable: YESNO N=171 McFadden R ² : 0.195361 Log-likelihood: -75.78780						

The mean value of Maximum Willingness to Pay of the sample people is 21 euros, with a confidence interval of (10.02, 31.97) obtained by delta method. This figure corresponds to the economic concept of equivalent variation since it means the Maximum Willingness to Pay for avoid an environmental damage. This valuation has only used valid responses excluding protest and doesn't know/doesn't answer responses.

Age, Education and Satisfaction variables are not significant. For this reason, a specification of the model excluding these variables has been considered.

3. Protest responses recoding valuation

In this paper the following way of acting is proposed. One person has a maximum willingness to pay for an environmental good conservation. Nevertheless, when a protest response is expressed nothing is revealed about it. Nonetheless, visitor is willing to incur a travel expense to enjoy the environment. This would constitute a minimum willingness to pay for the environmental good. If this travel expense, or minimum willingness to pay for enjoy the environmental good, is greater to the payment proposed in the valuation question, maximum willingness to pay for the environmental good will be greater too.

Given that a protest response does not mean a zero valuation, it could be assumed that people that incur in a travel cost to enjoy the good greater to the payment proposed, have a valuation of the good greater to the payment proposed in the valuation question. So, their response could be understood as a not revealed “yes”. Consequently, their response could be recoded as a yes to the proposed payment. Equally doesn't know/doesn't answer responses could be treated in this way. On the other hand, there is no certainty that people that incur a travel cost smaller than the proposed payment had a maximum willingness to pay smaller than the proposed bid, so they would still be excluded from the estimates.

Therefore, protest responses would be subjected to the following recoding process³:

³ Morrison et al. (2000) propose a recoding related to payment vehicle bias. They raise four questions to the protesters. One of them is if they could afford the payment; if they answer “no”, they recode them as opposed to the proposal (and the corresponding payment of 50\$). If they show that they would pay if it could be found another acceptable way of payment, if they could be convinced that the government does

If $C_i > B_i$, $YESNO_i = 1$ [4]

If $C_i \leq B_i$, protester “i” is excluded from the sample [5]

Where C_i is the travel expense of respondent i and B_i is the bid proposed in the valuation question.

This is probably a better option than to consider protest responses as real zero responses or to exclude them from the analysis. Following this new method, it will be considered as affirmative responses to the proposed bid in case of protestors revealing a travel expense greater to the payment proposed. Specifically, in this paper, given that the payment vehicle is an annual entrance, it has been compared the bid proposed to the respondent for an annual entrance (5,10,15 or 20 euros) with the travel expense made by respondent during the last year. That includes the travel cost of one visit multiplied by the number of visits made by respondent to the nature reserve during the last year.

From the 34 protest responses or doesn't know/doesn't answer responses, 21 correspond to respondents that have a expense in travels greater to the proposed bid. So, they could be included as affirmative responses in the contingent valuation exercise. Sample would raise from 171 to 192 valid enquires and protest or doesn't know/doesn't answer responses would reduce 62%. Extended sample estimates are included in Table 4.

not have funds or needs an extraordinary funding, are recoded as favorable to the proposal (with a 50\$ payment).

Table 4. Simple dichotomous format Contingent Valuation Model including significant variables and protest responses recoding

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	Statistic z	P > z	95% Confidence interval	
Bid	-0.1871323	0.0411407	-4.55	0.000	-0.2677665	-0.106498
Ntravel	0.1116716	0.0364923	3.06	0.002	0.040148	0.1831952
Constant	3.149454	0.6504212	4.84	0.000	1.874652	4.424256
Dependent Variable: YESNO N=192 McFadden R ² : 0.209451 Log-likelihood: -78.71762						

The mean of the maximum willingness to pay obtained with the sample that includes recoded protest responses (using expression [3]) is 22.43 euros, with a confidence interval (9.48, 35.38). This value is greater to the one obtained with the sample that excluded protest responses that was 21 euros. It is proved that this method allow to recover information that would be lost otherwise due to protest responses exclusion.

Bellow, this method results are compared to sample selection models ones, the only known alternative that uses protest responses information, and it is checked if this methodology has any advantage.

4. Sample selection model valuation

In sample selection models, two equations are defined that would be estimated simultaneously, selectivity equation and bid equation.

Therefore, binary variables are defined, Y_1 for the selectivity equation and Y_2 for bid equation, depending on two latent variables Y_1^* and Y_2^* respectively in such a way that

$$Y_1 = 1 \text{ if } Y_1^* > 0, \text{ if he decides to reveal his willingness to pay} \quad [6]$$

$$Y_1 = 0 \text{ if } Y_1^* \leq 0, \text{ if he decides not to reveal his willingness to pay (protest)} \quad [7]$$

$$Y_2 = 1 \text{ if } Y_2^* > t, \text{ if his willingness to pay is over the proposed bid } t \quad [8]$$

$$Y_2 = 0 \text{ if } Y_2^* \leq t, \text{ if his willingness to pay is under the proposed bid } t \quad [9]$$

The two choices are modeled simultaneously assuming a lineal specification, being x_1 and x_2 two vectors of respondent socioeconomic characteristics.

$$Y_1^* = x_1' + u_1 \quad [10]$$

$$Y_2^* = x_2' + u_2 \quad [11]$$

where u_1 and u_2 are two error terms distributed as a bivariate Normal

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \end{pmatrix} \sim N \left[\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1^2 & \sigma_{12} \\ \sigma_{12} & \sigma_2^2 \end{pmatrix} \right] \text{ where } \rho \text{ is correlation between } u_1 \text{ y } u_2, \sigma_1^2 \text{ is the variance}$$

of u_1^* , σ_2^2 is the variance of u_2^* and $\sigma_{12} = \rho\sigma_1\sigma_2$ is the covariance between u_1 y u_2 . Its

likelihood function can be written as follows:

$$L = \prod_{Y_1=0} P(Y_1^* \leq 0) \prod_{Y_1=1} \left[\prod_{Y_2=1} P(Y_1^* > 0, Y_2^* > t) \prod_{Y_2=0} P(Y_1^* > 0, Y_2^* \leq t) \right] \quad [12]$$

where $P(Y_1^* \leq 0)$ is not reveal maximum willingness to pay probability (and obtain a protest response), $P(Y_1^* > 0, Y_2^* > t)$ is the probability of giving an affirmative response to the proposed payment once it has been decided to reveal maximum willingness to pay and $P(Y_1^* > 0, Y_2^* \leq t)$ is the probability of giving a negative response to the proposed payment once it has been decided to reveal maximum willingness to pay.

It has to be considered what variables to include in the selectivity equation, that is, what variables could explain a protest behavior. Age, Sex, Education and Income have

support in the literature as variables that could influence in a protest behavior. So, Meyerhoff et al. (2013) find that older people show a bigger probability of giving a protest response and Calia and Strazzera (2001) and Fonta et al. (2010) use this variable in the selection equation of their models although in this last paper it is not very significant. García Llorente, Martín-López y Montes (2011) find that men and people with a lower level of education show a bigger probability of giving a protest response and Brower and Martín-Ortega (2012) include sex and education in the selection equation of their models although they are not significant. Meyerhoff et al. (2013) find that low income people show a bigger probability to give a protest response although in none of the five papers with sample selection models cited in this paper include Income in the selection equation. Ramajo-Hernández and Saz-Salazar (2012) and Saz-Salazar and Guaita-Pradas (2013) find that income is significant in selectivity and bid equation although sample selection bias is rejected in both studies and they use Spike models in their valuations. Nonetheless, none of these variables have been significant in the different models estimated in this paper, neither Ntravel nor Satisfaction. Only Cost has been significant; that's why only this variable will be finally included in the selectivity equation. Bid equation includes Ntravel (more travels means lower unit price per visit) and Bid as variables that explain the approval or refusal of the payment for the environmental good. Other variables are excluded as were in contingent model [2].

Once other explicative variables are dismissed, the following model will be estimated with the selectivity equation

$$Y_1^* = \beta_1 \text{Cost} + u_1 \quad [13]$$

and bid equation

$$Y_2^* = \beta_{21} \text{Bid} + \beta_{22} \text{Ntravel} + u_2 \quad [14]$$

whose estimates are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Sample selection model

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	Statistic z	P > z	95% Confidence interval	
Bid	-0.0950328	0.0280895	-3.38	0.001	-0.1500872	-0.0399785
Ntravel	0.0453211	0.0156642	2.89	0.004	0.0146198	0.0760224
Constant	1.432442	0.5199701	2.75	0.006	0.4133189	2.451564
Dependent Variable: YESNO						

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	Statistic z	P > z	95% Confidence interval	
Cost	0.0632395	0.0242033	2.61	0.009	0.0158019	0.110677
Constant	0.5119375	0.1931944	2.65	0.008	0.1332834	0.8905915
Athrho	0.9661231	0.90211	1.07	0.284	-0.80198	2.734226
rho	0.7469957	0.3987303			-0.6651423	0.9915999
LR test of indep. Eqns. (rho = 0) : chi2(1) = 1.26 Prob > chi2 = 0.2622						
Dependent Variable: Y ₁ Reveals N= 205 Wald chi2(2)=16.31 Log likelihood=-159.0133						

Using expression [3] and coefficients estimates, it can be obtained a valuation of 18.92 euros with a confidence interval of (9.74, 28.1). As rho has a positive value, this would indicate that, in the presence of a sample selection problem, model estimates excluding protest responses would produce an overestimate of the mean of maximum willingness to pay. This result would be in line with model [2] results that produce a value of 21 euros when excluding protest responses. Nonetheless, after estimating model [13]-[14], there are not evidences of a sample selection problem. The value of contrast statistical LR is 1.26 and p-value shows that null hypothesis cannot be rejected (LR statistical distributes as a chi-square with one freedom grade under $H_0: \rho = 0$).

One advantage of the recoding method proposed in this paper is that information is recovered even in those cases in which there is not a sample selection problem. So, applying this method, the valuation of the mean of the yearly maximum willingness to pay by one visitor is 22.43 euros, making more accurate the results of model [2] that produced a result of 21 euros excluding protest responses. In cases in which there was a sample selection problem, this could disappear or, at least, weaken, since the quantity of protest responses and interviews rejected would reduce. Unfortunately, the absence of sample selection problem in data used hinders to test if this problem had disappeared by using recoding. Another advantage of the proposed recoding is that it is a straightforward, intuitive and easy computation method. In contrast, Strazzera et al. (2003a) point out that the major drawback of sample selection models is computational complexity. Indeed, one of the principal difficulties is the identification of the model that is evident in no admissible ρ parameter estimate (out of the valid variation range for a correlation coefficient, this is $[-1,1]$). The appearance of this problem is frequent in sample selection models estimated by maximum likelihood. Therefore, model estimates in Strazzera et al. (2003b) produce a value for ρ of -0.933 and in Brouwer and Martín-Ortega (2012) of -1.554. These ρ values impede to dismiss identification problems.

5. Conclusions

In all the contingent valuation studies, there exists a more or less high rate of protest responses but there is not a protocol about how to treat them in the contingent valuation literature. In most cases they are excluded from estimates, what can cause biases in sample representativeness and willingness to pay means calculus.

In this paper, it is proposed one method to recode this kind of responses applicable to the simple dichotomous format valuation question made to visitors to the natural environment. Those respondents that give a protest response but have a travel cost greater than the bid proposed in the valuation question are recoded as an affirmative answer to the proposed payment. The economic justification lies in the minimum willingness to pay for enjoying the environment that travel cost reveals, while valuation question tries to obtain information about respondent's maximum willingness to pay.

It is an objective method (not subjected to an arbitrary researcher criterion), easily applicable and very intuitive. It allows to recover an important part of protest responses meaning that studies improve in representativeness because greater samples are available. Sample selectivity problems could be overcome but even if they did not exist, as this article case is, they allow recover information and improve estimates accuracy. It also avoids computational complexity associated to sample selection models and difficulties associated to likelihood function maximization.

References

- Atkinson, J., Morse-Jones, S., Mourato, S. and Provins, A. (2012). When to take No for an answer? Using Entreaties to reduce protests in Contingent Valuation Studies. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 51, 497-523.
- Bateman, I.J., Carson, R.T., Hanley, N., Day, B.H., Haneman, M., Hett, T., Jones-Lee, M., Loomes, G., Mourato, S., Ozdemiroglu, E., Pearce, D.W., Sugden, R. and Swanson, J. (2002). *Economic valuation with stated preference techniques: a manual*. Edward Elgar, Cheltenham.
- Bishop, R.C. and Heberlein, T.A. (1979). Measuring values of extra-market goods: are indirect measures biased? *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 61, 926-930.
- Bonnichsen, O. and Ladenburg, J. (2010). Using an Ex-ante Entreaty to Reduce Protest Zero Bias in Stated Preference Surveys-A Health Economic Case. *Journal of Choice Modelling*, 2(2), 200-215.
- Boyle, K.J., Welsh, M.P. and Bishop, R.C. (1993). The role of question order and respondent experience in contingent valuation studies. *Journal of Environmental Economic and Management* 25(1), 88-99.
- Boyle, K.J., MacDonald, H.F., Cheng, H.T. and McCollum, D.W. (1998). Bid design and yea saying in single-bounded dichotomous-choice questions. *Land Economics*, 74, 49-64.
- Brouwer, R. and Martín-Ortega, J. (2012). Modeling self-censoring of polluter pays protest votes in stated preference research to support resource damage

- estimations in environmental liability. *Resource and Energy Economics*, 34, 151-166.
- Calia, P. and Strazzer, E. (2001). A sample selection model for protest non-response votes in contingent valuation analyses. *Statistica* 61(3), 473-485.
- Clinch, J.P. and A. Murphy. 2001. "Modelling winners and losers in contingent valuation of public goods: appropriate welfare measures and econometric analysis". *The Economic Journal* 111, 420-443.
- Cooper, J.C. (1993). Optimal bid selection for dichotomous choice contingent valuation surveys. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 24, 25-40.
- Dziegielewska, D.A. and Mendelsohn, R. (2007). Does "No" means "No"? A protest methodology. *Environmental and Resource Economics* 38, 71-87.
- Fonta, W., Ichoku, E. and Kabubo-Mariara, J. (2010). The Effects of Protest Zeros on Estimates of Willingness to pay in Healthcare Contingent Valuation Analysis. *Applied Health Economics and Health Policy*, vol.8, n°4, 225-237.
- García-Llorente, M., Martín-López, B. and Montes, C. (2011). Exploring the motivations of protesters in contingent valuation: Insights for conservation policies. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 14, 76-88.
- Haneman, W.M. (1984). Welfare Evaluations in Contingent valuation Experiment with Discrete Responses. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, vol. 63, n°3, 332-341.

- Jaksonson, K.M. and Dragun, A.K. (2001). The worth of a possum: valuing species with the contingent valuation method. *Environmental and resource economics* 19, 211-227.
- Jorgensen, B.S., Syme, G.J., Bishop, B.J. and Nancarrow, B.E. (1999). Protest responses in contingent valuation. *Environmental and resource economics* 14(1), 131-150.
- Kriström, B. (1997). Spike models in contingent valuation. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 79, 1013-1023.
- Lindhjem, H. and Navrud, S. (2011). Are internet surveys an alternative to face-to-face interviews in contingent valuation? *Ecological Economics*, 70, 1628-1637.
- Meyerhoff, J. and Liebe, U. (2006). Protest beliefs in contingent valuation: Explaining their motivation. *Ecological Economics*, 57, 583-594.
- Meyerhoff, J. and Liebe, U. (2010). Determinants of protest responses in environmental valuation: A meta-study. *Ecological Economics*, 70, 366-374.
- Meyerhoff, J., Morkbak, M.R. and Olsen, S.B. (2013). A Meta-study Investigating the Sources of Protest Behaviour in Stated Preference Surveys. *Environmental and Resources Economics*, published online on July, 26.
- Mitchel, R.C. and Carson, R.T. (1989). Using surveys to value public goods: the contingent valuation method. *Resources for the future*. Washington.
- Morrison, M.D., Blamey, R.K. and Bennet, J.W. (2000). Minimising payment vehicle bias in contingent valuation studies. *Environmental and Resource Economics* 16, 407-422.

- Nunes, P. and Van den Bergh, J. (2004). Can People value protection against invasive marine species? Evidence from a joint TC-CV survey in the Netherlands. *Environmental and Resource Economics* 28, 517-532.
- Pemberton, C.A., Harris-Charles, E. and Patterson-Andrews, H. (2010). Cultural bias in contingent valuation of copper mining in the Commonwealth of Dominica. *Ecological Economics*, 70, 19-23.
- Ramajo-Hernández, J. and Saz-Salazar, S. (2012). Estimating the non-market benefits of water quality improvement for a case study in Spain: A contingent valuation approach. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 22, 47-59.
- Riera, P. (1994). *Manual de Valoración Contingente*. Instituto de estudios fiscales.
- Saz-Salazar, S. and Guaita-Pradas, I. (2013). On the value of drovers' routes as environmental assets: A contingent valuation approach. *Land Use Policy*, 32, 78-88.
- Strazzera, E., Genius, M., Scarpa, R. and Hutchinson, G (2003a). The Effect of Protest Votes on the Estimates of WTP for Use Values of recreational Sites. *Environmental and resource Economics* 25, 461-476.
- Strazzera, E., Scarpa, R., Calia, P., Garrod, G. and Willis, K. (2003b). Modelling zero values and protest responses in contingent valuation surveys. *Applied Economics*, vol. 35(2), 133-138.
- Szabo, Z. (2011). Reducing protest responses by deliberative monetary valuation: Improving the validity of biodiversity valuation. *Ecological economics* 72, 37-44.

Whittington, D., Smith, V.K., Okorafor, A., Okore, A., Liu, J.L. and McPhail, A.
(1992). Giving respondents time to think in contingent valuation studies: A
developing countries application. *Journal of Environmental Economics and
Management* 22(3), 205-225.

Appendix

Table 1. Simple dichotomous format Contingent Valuation Model including all socioeconomic variables and valid responses

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	Statistic z	P > z	95% Confidence interval	
Bid	-0.1728006	0.0417102	-4.14	0.000	-0.2545511	-0.0910501
Ntravel	0.0954584	0.0382518	2.50	0.013	0.0204863	0.1704305
Income	0.1264164	0.269717	0.47	0.639	-0.4022191	0.655052
Age	-0.011748	0.0227891	-0.52	0.606	-0.0564139	0.0329178
Education	-0.085977	0.2879701	-0.30	0.765	-0.650388	0.478434
Satisfaction	-0.2248542	0.4297878	-0.52	0.601	-1.067223	0.6175145
Constant	3.497411	1.270893	2.75	0.006	1.006506	5.988315
Dependent Variable: YESNO N=171 McFadden R ² : 0.187628 Log-likelihood: -71.25227						